

A Privacy-Preserving and Efficient Driver Recognition Framework for Sustainable ITS using DRL and FL

Andreou Andreas
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
andreou.andreas@unic.ac.cy

Constandinos X. Mavromoustakis
Department of Computer Science
University of Nicosia
Nicosia, Cyprus
mavromoustakis.c@unic.ac.cy

Evangelos Markakis
Department of Electrical and
Computer Engineering
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
markakis@pasiphae.eu

Athina Bourdena
Department of Business
Administration and Tourism
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Heraklion, Crete, Greece
bourdena@hmu.gr

George Mastorakis
Department of Management Science
and Technology
Hellenic Mediterranean University
Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece
gmastorakis@hmu.gr

Abstract—In Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), driver recognition presents challenges of data privacy, computational efficiency, and energy consumption. Optimizing energy use in ITS has become crucial with the rise of environmentally conscious Information and Communication Technology (ICT) practices. Therefore, this paper introduces a privacy-preserving and energy-efficient task offloading strategy using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) and Federated Learning (FL) within a network leveraging Smart Traffic Cameras (STCs) for edge computing. Initially, the public transports employ a DRL-based strategy to offload tasks to STCs, optimizing network resources and minimizing energy use. At the second phase, allows private vehicles to train models locally, offloading only model parameters, thus ensuring data privacy and reducing communication energy costs. Finally, aggregates these parameters at a central cloud server, refining a Network-Wide Model (NWM). The proposed framework enhances model performance, preserves privacy, and improves computational efficiency, reducing the carbon footprint of ITS operations. Simulations demonstrate that DRL's Actor-Critic Algorithm (ACA) reduces task latency and energy consumption while FL ensures efficient model training with minimal communication overhead.

Index Terms—ITS, DRL, FL, Data Privacy, Task Offloading, Smart Traffic Cameras, Edge Computing, Actor-Critic Algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), recognizing the identity of drivers is essential for enhancing security, personalizing in-car experiences, and monitoring compliance [1]. However, this process presents two primary challenges: ensuring data privacy and efficiently offloading tasks for model training across vehicles with different privacy requirements. Sensitive data, such as biometric information collected from private vehicles, must be safeguarded to comply with privacy standards

and prevent unauthorized use while maintaining efficient driver identity recognition across a network of vehicles.

Therefore, to tackle these challenges, this paper proposes a three-phase task offloading strategy using Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) and Federated Learning (FL) within a network that utilizes Smart Traffic Cameras (STCs) [2] - [4]. Unlike traditional methods that use Roadside Units (RSUs) for computational offloading, STCs serve as edge devices, optimizing network resources and enhancing model training efficiency [5].

Initially, public transports, such as public buses or taxis, employ a DRL-based scheme to offload selected data related to driver's identity to nearby STCs [6]. This approach leverages the edge computing capabilities of STCs to improve computational efficiency and model accuracy. At phase two, private vehicles prioritize data privacy, perform local model training, and offload only model parameters to STCs. It ensures that sensitive biometric data remains within the vehicle while contributing to the training of the Network-Wide Model (NWM). Finally, for the third phase, a central cloud server aggregates the model parameters received from STCs, refines an NWM, and distributes it back to the vehicles for further improvement. Thus, the proposed collaborative framework enhances model performance, preserves privacy, and ensures computational efficiency.

The contributions of this research work includes a DRL-based partial task offloading strategy for public transports to minimize latency and a dual-layer FL scheme for private vehicles to maintain privacy while enabling practical model training. The experimental results demonstrate that this hybrid approach significantly reduces latency for public transports and improves training efficiency for private vehicles, offering a scalable and communication-efficient solution for driver identity recognition

in ITS.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have explored task offloading and optimization strategies for the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) environment. In [7], a privacy-preserving reputation updating scheme was proposed for cloud-assisted vehicular networks. This scheme utilizes task offloading to reduce the computational and communication burdens on the Trusted Authority by 88.36% and 83.88%, respectively, leveraging elliptic curve cryptography and Paillier algorithms for secure and efficient management.

Similarly, an edge collaborative task offloading and splitting strategy was introduced for MEC-enabled 5G IoV networks in [8]. The strategy optimizes task splitting and uplink transmit power to minimize latency and energy consumption. An alternate convex search algorithm was used to solve the problem, achieving lower costs than baseline algorithms. In [9], a joint on-board task offloading and job scheduling method for cloud-edge computing was presented. Utilizing Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication and ant colony optimization, this method optimizes task offloading, reduces congestion, and enhances Quality of Service (QoS).

Furthermore, [10] proposed traffic-aware intelligent sleep decision-making algorithms for edge servers in 6G-enabled IoV networks using DRL and FL. These algorithms dynamically manage server operations, reducing system costs by up to 45.36%. Xiao et al. [11] tackled task offloading in 5G-enabled cloud-edge environments, optimizing energy consumption through iterative decoupling. In contrast, Huang et al. [12] proposed a DRL-based algorithm for optimizing computation offloading in dynamic IoV environments, showing superior simulation performance.

Andreou and Mavromoustakis et al. [13] focused on emergency communication in 6G+ networks, utilizing multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient algorithms to enhance system efficiency. Hararika et al. [14] introduced a multi-agent DRL-based task offloading strategy for IoV, improving resource allocation and task completion rates. A survey by [15] reviewed advancements in FL for connected vehicles, while [16] proposed a three-layer FL model with optimization algorithms to improve learning accuracy in dynamic IoV networks.

A. Gaps and Motivation

Despite notable advancements in task offloading and FL for vehicular applications, several challenges persist, particularly in balancing data privacy and computational efficiency for tasks such as driver identity recognition. Traditional task offloading strategies tend to focus on optimizing computational resources but often neglect the critical privacy concerns associated with transmitting sensitive data, such as biometric information. This is especially problematic in ITS, where diverse privacy requirements exist across public and private vehicles. Moreover, existing FL frameworks are not fully optimized for handling these heterogeneous privacy needs, particularly in mixed vehicular networks. They often struggle to balance the trade-offs

between computational efficiency, energy consumption, and privacy preservation, especially in real-time, resource-constrained environments. Therefore, there is a need for a more robust and adaptable approach that can seamlessly integrate privacy-preserving mechanisms with energy-efficient computational offloading in such complex, dynamic networks. This motivates the development of a hybrid solution that leverages both edge computing and intelligent offloading to address these gaps.

B. Proposed Approach

The proposed approach begins with a DRL-based scheme to optimize task offloading for public transport vehicles, modeled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) considering factors such as vehicle-to-STC distance, task size, and network conditions [17]. The system dynamically adjusts offloading decisions to minimize latency and energy consumption, optimizing resource use based on real-time conditions. In the next phase, private vehicles utilize a dual-layer FL framework to protect data privacy. Instead of transmitting raw biometric data, they locally train models and offload only model parameters to STCs for aggregation, ensuring sensitive data remains within the vehicle. Finally, aggregated model parameters from both public and private vehicles are sent to a central cloud server, where a global NWM is updated. This process enhances driver recognition accuracy while preserving privacy and computational efficiency across the entire network.

III. SYSTEM MODEL & PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Model

In the proposed ITS model, vehicles are categorized into private and public, each with distinct privacy needs and computational capabilities. The system aims to develop efficient data processing and task offloading strategies tailored to each vehicle type. For public transports, the primary objective is to reduce computational load by offloading tasks to Smart Traffic Cameras (STCs), minimizing local computation and latency. Task offloading decisions depend on factors like task size, network conditions, and STC availability. Private vehicles prioritize data privacy, conducting local model training and only offloading model parameters (not raw data) to STCs for aggregation. This approach protects sensitive information while ensuring efficient driver identity recognition, balancing privacy and computational efficiency across the ITS network.

As depicted in Fig. 1 the proposed system model is divided into three parts. Initially, the cloud server aggregates all model parameters from STCs—both those from public transports and aggregated parameters from private vehicles. It updates the NWM and distributes it back to the vehicles for further refinement. The public transports offload local data to STCs, which collaboratively train models using the data. In contrast, private vehicles train their models locally and offload only model parameters to STCs for aggregation.

The network structure is clearly defined to manage this complex system involving multiple vehicles and STCs, with each component playing a specific role. Let $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ denote the private vehicles, $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ denote the public transports,

Fig. 1. Proposed Framework under ITS Environment

and $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ the STCs. The central cloud server is denoted as e , while the overall local dataset comprises private and public transport datasets, denoted as D_n and D_m , respectively, with no intersections between the datasets of different vehicles to ensure privacy.

B. Task Offloading for public transports

Due to limited computational resources, public transports may not be able to complete the driver recognition task within a tolerable latency threshold if processed locally. Therefore, these vehicles can partially offload tasks to the STCs as the offloading strategy minimizes latency by optimizing the trade-off between local computation and offloading.

Based on the communication model the upload rate $r_{k,n}$ for offloading a task from public transport n to STC k is defined by eq. (1)

$$r_{k,n} = \frac{B}{\ln 2} \ln \left(\frac{\sigma^2 + \xi + Pl_{k,n}h}{\sigma^2 + \xi} \right), \quad (1)$$

where B is the communication bandwidth, P is the transmit power, $l_{k,n}$ is the path-loss fading, h is the channel gain, σ^2 is the Gaussian noise power, and ξ is the communication interference.

If a task is computed locally on public transport n , the local computing delay t_n^0 is given by eq. (2)

$$t_n^0 = \frac{(1 - \xi_n)D_n C_n}{f_n^1}, \quad (2)$$

where D_n is the amount of data, C_n is the computational cycles needed per bit, and f_n^1 is the allocated computing resource.

When public transport n offloads a part ξ_n of its task to STC k , the total delay includes the data upload delay $t_{k,n}^1$ and the computation delay $t_{k,n}^2$ at STC k as given by eq. (3)

$$t_{k,n}^1 = \frac{\theta_{k,n} \xi_n D_n}{r_{k,n}}, \quad t_{k,n}^2 = \frac{\theta_{k,n} \xi_n D_n C_k}{f_{k,n}^2}, \quad (3)$$

where C_k is the computation cycles required by STC k , and $f_{k,n}^2$ is the computing resource allocated by STC k .

For the optimization problem regarding public transports, the objective is to minimize the average delay of tasks for all public transports using eq. (4)

$$\bar{t}_{\min} = \min_{\xi} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N T_n, \quad (4)$$

while the subject to constraints on node connections, computational resources, and task completion time.

C. Task Processing for Private Vehicles

The central cloud server e handles NWM aggregation and caching, while STCs aggregate model parameters from connected private vehicles. The dual-layer FL framework ensures data privacy by only transmitting model parameters, not raw data, allowing effective knowledge sharing while protecting sensitive information. Hence, the proposed framework enhances collaborative training and improves overall model generalization capabilities.

D. Cross-Vehicle Collaborative Model Aggregation

In cross-vehicle collaboration, public transports and STCs follow a single-layer FL architecture, while private vehicles follow a dual-layer FL architecture for model aggregation. The final NWM is obtained by aggregating model parameters from public and private vehicles at the central cloud server. This aggregation approach integrates models from different vehicle types, enhancing the robustness and accuracy of driver identity recognition in ITS. The system uses a transfer learning approach with pre-trained models and a CNN-based architecture optimized for computational efficiency to accurately recognize driver identities while minimizing latency and ensuring data privacy. This solution provides a scalable and privacy-preserving framework for ITS driver recognition applications.

IV. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The framework comprises DRL-based task offloading for public transports, FL-based model training for private vehicles, and an NWM aggregation strategy at the central cloud server. Each component addresses specific challenges related to data privacy, computational efficiency, and communication overhead in the ITS environment.

A. DRL for public transport task offloading

The DRL framework optimizes the task offloading decisions for public transports by dynamically adjusting to the network state, vehicle mobility, and task priorities. The problem is formulated as a MDP with the state space $S = (L, D, \bar{t})$ represents the distance set L between public transport n and STC k , the data size D to be offloaded, and the average latency \bar{t} to complete all public transport tasks. Therefore, ensures that the system state is manageable without incurring excessive overhead from observing the entire network. The action space $A = \xi$ defines the task offloading policy for all public transports. Unlike traditional binary offloading schemes, the action space in our approach is continuous, allowing tasks to be offloaded at any ratio, providing greater flexibility and better utilization of available resources.

Algorithm 1 Integrated Framework for DRL-Based Offloading and FL for ITS

Initialize: Actor network parameters θ ; Critic network parameters ϑ, ϑ' ; Target critic network parameters $\hat{\vartheta}$; Replay buffer R ; NWM parameters ϕ_e^{w*}

Set: I_{\max}, ε_0

repeat

for $i \leq I_{\max}$ **do**

for condition step **do**

$A \sim g^*$

 Take action A , observe new driver S' and reward R

 Update: $R \leftarrow (S, A, R, S') \cup R$

end for

if model training **then**

$(s, a, r, s') \sim R$

$R'(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (9)$

$Q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow (7)$

$V(s_t) \leftarrow (8)$

 Update: $\hat{\vartheta}, \theta$

end if

for each round of FL **do**

for $k \in K$ **do**

for $n \in N$ **do**

if $\theta_{k,n} = 1$ **then**

 Offload task n to k with ratio ξ_n

 Update: ϕ_n^l and $\phi_k^l \leftarrow (13)$

end if

end for

for $m \in M$ **do**

if m is connected to STC k **then**

 Update: $\phi_m^l \leftarrow (13)$

end if

end for

$\phi_{\alpha,e,t} \leftarrow (10)$

end for

$\phi_{w,e,t} \leftarrow (11)$

$\phi_{l,*t+1} \leftarrow (12)$

end for

end for

until convergence or $i = I_{\max}$

Output: Optimal policy parameters θ^* , critic network parameters $\hat{\vartheta}^*$, and NWM parameters ϕ_e^{w*}

Also, the reward function $R(S, A) = -\bar{t}$ is inversely proportional to the average task completion latency. A higher reward indicates a more efficient task offloading policy that reduces overall latency for public transport.

The proposed framework employs the ACA, which aims to find the optimal policy $g(a|s)$ that maximizes the expected future return while ensuring exploration by maximizing policy entropy. The core objective of the ACA algorithm is to maximize the expected return function given by eq.(5) with an entropy term.

$$F(g) = \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim \rho^g} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \mathbb{E}_{a \sim g(\cdot|s)} [\log(g(a|s))]) \right], \quad (5)$$

where $r(s_t, a_t)$ is the immediate reward, γ is the discount factor, α is a temperature parameter, and $-\mathbb{E}_{a \sim g(\cdot|s)} [\log(g(a|s))]$ represents the entropy of the policy. The optimization of policy g is given by eq.(6)

$$g^* = \arg \max_g \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \rho^g, a_t \sim g} [Q(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log(g(a_t|s_t))]. \quad (6)$$

ACA balances exploration and exploitation by incorporating policy entropy into the decision-making process. The core component of the ACA algorithm is the Q-function, given by eq.(7), which is updated using a variant of the Bellman equation that takes into account policy entropy

$$Q(s_t, a_t) = r(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s_{t+1} \sim \rho} [V(s_{t+1})], \quad (7)$$

where the value function $V(s_t)$ is defined by eq.(8).

$$V(s_t) = \mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim g} [Q(s_t, a_t) - \alpha \log(g(a_t|s_t))] \quad (8)$$

In the context of ITS, where different types of vehicles have varying offloading strategies and privacy requirements, the ACA algorithm is adjusted to fit this environment better. Therefore, to achieve this, a fine-tuned reward mechanism is introduced to differentiate between offloading policies. Two baseline policies are defined as reference points for the learning process. The total offloading policy, where all tasks are offloaded, is defined as $g_t(a_{\max}|s) = 1$, with $a_{\max} = 1$. Conversely, the total no-offloading policy, where no tasks are offloaded, is defined as $g_n(a_{\min}|s) = 1$, with $a_{\min} = 0$.

To enhance the effectiveness of the ACA-based offloading strategy, the reward function as given by eq.(9) is adjusted to reflect better the performance of policies relative to these baseline strategies. The adjusted reward function is designed to encourage the learning of policies that outperform these baselines, thereby enhancing learning efficiency and adaptability in the dynamic ITS environment.

$$R'(s_t, a_t) = R(s_t, a_t) + \gamma_l \cdot \max(0, Q^g(s_t, a_t) - Q^{g_t}(s_t, a_{\max})) + \gamma_n \cdot \max(0, Q^g(s_t, a_t) - Q^{g_n}(s_t, a_{\min})), \quad (9)$$

where $R'(s_t, a_t)$ is the adjusted reward, $R(s_t, a_t)$ denotes the original reward, while γ_l and γ_n are weighting coefficients. The $\max(0, \cdot)$ is a maximization function that provides additional positive rewards only when the current policy exceeds the baseline policies, while the $Q^{g_t}(s_t, a_{\max})$ and the $Q^{g_n}(s_t, a_{\min})$ denotes the action-value functions of the baseline policies.

B. Private Vehicles to STCs for FL

FL is employed for private vehicles to ensure data privacy while enabling collaborative model training. These vehicles perform local model training and only offload model parameters

to STCs for aggregation, preventing the transmission of sensitive biometric data.

The training process for private vehicles is structured as a dual-layer FL framework. Each private vehicle $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ trains a local driver recognition model using its dataset D_m . The regional model parameters $\phi_{l,m,t}$ are updated based on the vehicle's driving data. Private vehicles offload their updated model parameters to the connected STC k for aggregation. Each STC aggregates the model parameters received from private vehicles and sends the aggregated parameters $\phi_{\alpha,k,t}$ to the central cloud server for further aggregation.

C. Model Aggregation Strategies for the Central Cloud Server in Federated Learning

The central cloud server, denoted as e , performs network-wide aggregation of model parameters received from STCs to update the driver's recognition model. The aggregation strategy ensures the effective integration of models from the vehicles.

1) *NWM Aggregation*: The aggregation process at the central cloud server is formulated by eq.(10)

$$\phi_{\alpha,e,t} = \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \phi_{\alpha,k,t}, \quad (10)$$

where $\phi_{\alpha,k,t}$ represents the aggregated model parameters from STC k , and γ_k is the weight coefficient. The NWM $\phi_{w,e,t}$ is further updated by incorporating the parameters from public transports and other STCs given by eq.(11)

$$\phi_{w,e,t} = \sum_{n=1}^N \gamma_n \phi_{l,n,t} + \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma'_k \phi_{l,k,t} + \sum_{k=1}^K \gamma_k \phi_{\alpha,k,t}. \quad (11)$$

After aggregation, the central server e sends the updated NWM parameters back to the clients, which include public vehicles N , private vehicles M , and STCs K . Each client updates its local model given by eq.(12) to reflect the results of the global learning.

$$\phi_{l,*,t+1} = \phi_{w,e,t} \quad (12)$$

Assume that each client (including public vehicles N , private vehicles M , and STCs K) has a pre-trained model. The objective is to minimize the client's local loss function L_* , which depends on the client's local dataset and model parameters. The local model update formula based on Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is expressed by eq.(13)

$$\phi_{l,*,t+2} = \phi_{l,*,t+1} - \eta \nabla L_*(\phi_{l,*,t+1}), \quad (13)$$

where $\phi_{l,*,t+1}$ represents the model parameters of the client at time step $(t+1)$, η is the learning rate and satisfies $\eta > 0$, and $\nabla L_*(\phi_{l,*,t+1})$ is the gradient of the loss function L_* with respect to the model parameters $\phi_{l,*,t+1}$, typically computed over the client's local dataset.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To verify the advantages of the proposed partial offloading strategy, we compare it with the local computation scheme, the complete offloading scheme and the task offloading strategy based on the twin delayed deep Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. The simulation environment parameters are presented in Table I.

TABLE I
SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT PARAMETERS

Parameter Description	Notation/Value
Number of public vehicles	$N = 20$
Number of STCs	$K = 10$
Public vehicle distribution range	500 m
Path loss exponent	$\delta = 3$
Wireless channel bandwidth	$B = 350$ Hz
Public vehicle transmit power	$P = 3$ W
Channel instantaneous power	$h = 3$
Gaussian white noise power	$\sigma^2 = 4 \times 10^{-13}$ W
Channel interference	$\xi = 1 \times 10^{-14}$ W
Computational cycles for public vehicles	$C_n = 4$ cycles/bit
Computational cycles for STCs	$C_k = 3$ cycles/bit
Public vehicle computational resources	$f_n^1 = 2.5 \times 10^3$ Hz
STC computational resources	$F_k^2 = 1 \times 10^4$ Hz
Task size range	[400, 600]
Maximum allowable delay	$T_{\max} = 100$ ms

The experimental results showed that the ACA strategy consistently outperforms other task-offloading strategies—PPO, local computing, and full offloading—across various scenarios. Fig. 2(a) illustrates the average delay experienced by public vehicles with varying numbers. The ACA strategy consistently achieves the lowest average delay, indicating its ability to effectively balance the load between local computation and offloading to STCs. In contrast, the Full Offloading strategy shows a significant increase in delay as the number of vehicles increases due to congestion and limited resources at the STCs. Fig. 2(b) examines the impact of the number of STCs on average delay. The ACA strategy maintains a consistently low delay regardless of the number of STCs, demonstrating its dynamic adaptability to changes in the network environment.

Fig. 2(c) shows the effect of varying computational resources for public vehicles on average delay. As computational resources increase, the ACA strategy effectively reduces delay, demonstrating superior utilization of local resources. PPO also shows a decreasing trend in delay but is less efficient than ACA. The full offloading strategy remains unaffected by changes in local resources, as all tasks are offloaded to STCs. Fig. 2(d) explores how the computational resources available at STCs impact the average delay. The ACA strategy remains stable and efficient across varying resource levels. In contrast, the full offloading strategy shows a notable decrease in delay with increased STC resources, indicating its limitations without adequate capacity.

Fig. 3 presents the convergence performance of the ACA algorithm with different learning rates. The ACA algorithm demonstrates reliable convergence, with higher learning rates offering faster convergence but potential initial instability. Overall, the ACA strategy is the most stable, adaptable, and efficient task-offloading strategy for ITS.

Fig. 2. Average Delay for: (a) Different Numbers of public Vehicles, (b) Different Numbers of STCs, (c) Different Computational Resources of public Vehicles, (d) Different Computational Resources of STCs

Fig. 3. Convergence Performance of ACA

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This paper introduced a hybrid framework for computational task offloading in ITS, combining DRL and FL. The ACA was utilized to efficiently manage task offloading. Simulations show that ACA significantly outperforms other strategies, such as PPO, local computation and complete offloading schemes. It excels in reducing average delay, ensuring system stability, adapting to different computational resources and workloads. While PPO performed adequately, ACA proved more effective in managing high computational loads and consistently demonstrated reliable convergence across varied ITS scenarios. Future work will explore multi-agent reinforcement learning to enhance collaboration between vehicles and STCs, incorporate real-world vehicular mobility patterns, and integrate advanced security

measures like differential privacy for secure task offloading.

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